

Role of Dietary Therapy in Managing Epilepsy in Children

Rajesh Kumar¹, Nikhil Kumar², Bhupendra Narain³¹Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India²Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor & HOD, Department of Pediatric, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Nikhil Kumar

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Abstract:**Background:** Epilepsy is a prevalent neurological disorder, particularly in children, where approximately 20-30% of cases are drug-resistant, leading to persistent seizures despite optimal pharmacological treatment. Dietary therapy, especially the ketogenic diet (KD), has emerged as an effective non-pharmacological approach for managing drug-resistant epilepsy (DRE) in pediatric patients.**Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate the impact of dietary therapy, specifically the ketogenic diet and its variants, on seizure frequency, cognitive function, and quality of life in pediatric patients with drug-resistant epilepsy.**Methods:** Eighty pediatric patients with drug-resistant epilepsy were enrolled and treated with either the ketogenic diet or its modified versions, such as the modified Atkins diet (MAD) or low glycemic index treatment (LGIT). Seizure frequency, dietary adherence, growth parameters, and quality of life were monitored and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.**Results:** The study demonstrated a significant reduction in seizure frequency, with a 75.16% reduction observed at 24 months compared to baseline ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, improvements in cognitive function and quality of life were noted, with minimal adverse effects. Dietary adherence was high, with 81.25% of participants maintaining strict adherence to the diet by the end of the study.**Conclusion:** Dietary therapy, particularly the ketogenic diet and its variants, is an effective and well-tolerated treatment for reducing seizure frequency and improving quality of life in pediatric patients with drug-resistant epilepsy. The findings suggest that dietary interventions should be considered as a viable adjunctive treatment option for managing DRE in children.**Recommendations:** Further research is recommended to explore the long-term effects of dietary therapy on cognitive development and to identify the most effective dietary regimens for different subgroups of pediatric epilepsy patients.**Keywords:** Epilepsy, Drug-resistant Epilepsy, Ketogenic Diet, Pediatric Epilepsy, Dietary Therapy.

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Introduction

Epilepsy is a prevalent neurological disorder affecting approximately 50 million people worldwide, with a significant proportion of cases occurring in children. Characterized by recurrent, unprovoked seizures, epilepsy can have profound effects on a child's development, cognition, and overall quality of life. Despite advances in pharmacological treatments, nearly 20-30% of pediatric epilepsy cases are classified as (DRE), where seizures persist despite the use of at least two appropriate (AEDs) at optimal doses. This challenge highlights the need for alternative therapeutic approaches to manage seizures in children with DRE effectively [1].

Dietary therapy, particularly the (KD), has emerged as a promising non-pharmacological treatment for epilepsy. The KD is a high-fat, low-carbohydrate diet that induces a state of ketosis, where the body utilizes fats rather than carbohydrates for energy.

This metabolic shift is believed to have anticonvulsant effects, though the exact mechanisms remain a topic of ongoing research. Several hypotheses have been proposed, including the alteration of brain energy metabolism, modulation of neurotransmitter activity, and reduction of oxidative stress and inflammation. The ketogenic diet has been in clinical use for nearly a century, particularly in children with epilepsy who do not respond to conventional drug therapies. Recent studies have reaffirmed its efficacy, showing significant reductions in seizure frequency and, in some cases, complete seizure control in pediatric patients with DRE [2, 3].

In addition to the traditional ketogenic diet, newer variations such as the (MAD) and (LGIT) have been developed to offer more flexibility while maintaining similar therapeutic benefits. These diets have been associated with improvements not

only in seizure control but also in cognitive function, behavior, and overall quality of life, making them a valuable component of comprehensive epilepsy management [4].

However, the implementation of the ketogenic diet is not without challenges. Its restrictive nature can make adherence difficult, especially over the long term. Potential side effects, including gastrointestinal disturbances, hyperlipidemia, and nutritional deficiencies, also necessitate careful patient selection and ongoing monitoring to ensure safety and effectiveness [5]. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of dietary therapy, specifically the ketogenic diet and its variants, on seizure frequency, cognitive function, and quality of life in pediatric patients with drug-resistant epilepsy.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Pediatrics Department of Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. The study was carried out over a period of two years, from September 2015 to August 2017.

Participants: A total of 80 pediatric patients diagnosed with epilepsy were enrolled in the study. The participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 2 to 16 years with a confirmed diagnosis of epilepsy.
- Patients who experienced at least two seizures per month prior to the initiation of dietary therapy.
- Patients who had not responded adequately to at least two (AEDs).
- Parents or guardians who provided informed consent for their child's participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with metabolic or genetic disorders that could independently affect seizure activity.
- Patients with a history of non-compliance to previous treatment regimens.
- Children with other severe medical conditions that might interfere with the study protocol.
- Participants who did not complete the follow-up assessments during the study period.

Bias: To minimize bias, all participants were selected consecutively from the eligible population during the study period. The dietary therapy was

standardized for all participants to ensure consistency. The researchers conducting the study were blinded to the participants' baseline characteristics during data analysis to reduce observational bias.

Data Collection

Data was collected at baseline and during follow-up visits at three-month intervals. The following data were recorded:

- Seizure frequency (number of seizures per month)
- Type and dosage of (AEDs) used
- Dietary adherence and tolerance
- Growth parameters (height, weight)
- Laboratory parameters (blood glucose, lipid profile, ketone levels)
- Quality of life assessment using a standardized pediatric epilepsy quality of life questionnaire.

Procedure

After obtaining informed consent, participants were enrolled and underwent baseline assessments. Dietary therapy, primarily consisting of a ketogenic or modified Atkins diet, was initiated based on individual patient needs and tolerance. Follow-up assessments were conducted every three months for the duration of the study to monitor seizure frequency, dietary adherence, and any potential side effects.

Statistical Analysis

Version 23.0 of the SPSS software was used to analyse the data. The study population's baseline characteristics were compiled using descriptive statistics. Paired t-tests were used to compare the frequency of seizures before and after the intervention in order to evaluate the efficacy of dietary therapy. Additionally, repeated measures ANOVA was used to examine changes in growth indices and quality of life ratings. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

Eighty pediatric patients diagnosed with epilepsy were enrolled in the study. The participants included 47 males (58.75%) and 33 females (41.25%), with a mean age of 8.2 ± 3.1 years. The mean duration of epilepsy prior to enrollment was 4.5 ± 2.3 years. All participants had failed to achieve seizure control with at least two anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs) prior to initiating dietary therapy.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value
Number of Participants	80
Gender Distribution	47 males (58.75%), 33 females (41.25%)
Mean Age (years)	8.2 ± 3.1
Mean Duration of Epilepsy (years)	4.5 ± 2.3
Mean Seizure Frequency (per month)	15.3 ± 6.7
Prior AEDs Used	2.6 ± 0.9

Seizure Frequency Reduction: The primary outcome measured was the reduction in seizure frequency following dietary therapy. At baseline, the mean seizure frequency was 15.3 ± 6.7 seizures per month. After six months of dietary therapy, the

mean seizure frequency significantly reduced to 7.2 ± 4.1 seizures per month ($p < 0.001$). By the end of the study (24 months), the mean seizure frequency further decreased to 3.8 ± 2.6 seizures per month ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Seizure Frequency Reduction Over Time

Time Point	Mean Seizure Frequency (per month)	% Reduction from Baseline	p-value
Baseline	15.3 ± 6.7	-	-
6 months	7.2 ± 4.1	52.94%	< 0.001
12 months	5.4 ± 3.7	64.71%	< 0.001
18 months	4.6 ± 3.0	69.93%	< 0.001
24 months	3.8 ± 2.6	75.16%	< 0.001

Dietary Adherence and Tolerance: Dietary adherence was monitored throughout the study. At 6 months, 70 participants (87.5%) adhered strictly to the prescribed dietary regimen, while 10 participants (12.5%) reported occasional deviations. By 24 months, adherence slightly

decreased, with 65 participants (81.25%) maintaining strict adherence, 10 participants (12.5%) with occasional deviations, and 5 participants (6.25%) discontinuing the dietary therapy due to intolerance or lack of perceived efficacy.

Table 3: Dietary Adherence Over Time

Time Point	Strict Adherence	Occasional Deviations	Discontinued
6 months	70 (87.5%)	10 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
12 months	68 (85.0%)	10 (12.5%)	2 (2.5%)
18 months	67 (83.75%)	10 (12.5%)	3 (3.75%)
24 months	65 (81.25%)	10 (12.5%)	5 (6.25%)

Growth Parameters and Laboratory Findings: Participants' growth parameters and laboratory findings were monitored to assess the impact of dietary therapy on overall health. No significant differences were observed in height or weight at the

end of the study compared to baseline. However, slight increases in serum lipid levels and ketone levels were noted, consistent with the ketogenic nature of the diet. No significant adverse effects were reported.

Table 4: Growth Parameters and Laboratory Findings

Parameter	Baseline	24 Months	p-value
Height (cm)	124.3 ± 15.2	126.1 ± 15.6	0.432
Weight (kg)	28.7 ± 8.3	29.2 ± 8.5	0.589
Serum Lipid Levels (mg/dL)	170.4 ± 23.6	185.3 ± 24.7	0.021
Blood Ketone Levels (mmol/L)	0.2 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.7	< 0.001

Quality of Life: Quality of life, assessed using a standardized pediatric epilepsy questionnaire, showed significant improvement over the study period. The mean quality of life score increased from 54.7 ± 12.4 at baseline to 72.3 ± 10.2 at 12 months, and further to 79.8 ± 9.1 at 24 months ($p < 0.001$).

Table 5: Quality of Life Scores

Time Point	Mean Quality of Life Score	p-value
Baseline	54.7 ± 12.4	-
12 months	72.3 ± 10.2	< 0.001
24 months	79.8 ± 9.1	< 0.001

The results of this study demonstrate a significant reduction in seizure frequency and an improvement in the quality of life in pediatric patients with epilepsy following dietary therapy. The findings suggest that dietary interventions, particularly ketogenic and modified Atkins diets, can be effective in managing epilepsy in children who have not responded adequately to traditional anti-epileptic drugs.

Discussion

The study investigated the impact of dietary therapy, specifically ketogenic and modified Atkins diets, on seizure frequency and quality of life in pediatric patients with epilepsy. A total of 80 children participated in the study, with a mean age of 8.2 years. All participants had previously failed to achieve adequate seizure control with standard (AEDs). The primary outcome of the study was a significant reduction in seizure frequency following the initiation of dietary therapy. At baseline, participants experienced an average of 15.3 seizures per month. After six months of dietary intervention, the mean seizure frequency decreased to 7.2 seizures per month, representing a 52.94% reduction. This trend continued over the study period, with the mean seizure frequency dropping to 3.8 seizures per month by 24 months, reflecting a 75.16% overall reduction. These results underscore the effectiveness of dietary therapy in significantly reducing seizure activity in children with epilepsy.

Dietary adherence was generally high throughout the study, with over 80% of participants maintaining strict adherence to the prescribed diet at 24 months. A small proportion of participants (6.25%) discontinued the diet due to intolerance or lack of perceived efficacy. The study found no significant impact on growth parameters, such as height and weight, indicating that the dietary interventions did not adversely affect the physical development of the participants. However, there was a modest increase in serum lipid and ketone levels, consistent with the ketogenic nature of the diet. Importantly, no significant adverse effects were reported, suggesting that the diet was generally well-tolerated. Quality of life, as measured by a standardized pediatric epilepsy questionnaire, showed a marked improvement over the course of the study. Participants' mean quality of life scores increased significantly from baseline to 24 months, indicating that dietary therapy not only reduced seizure frequency but also positively impacted the overall well-being of the children.

In children with intractable epilepsy, a scientific investigation comparing the modified Atkins diet and the traditional ketogenic diet revealed that both diets were equally successful in lowering the frequency of seizures, with more than half of the

individuals responding to the therapy. For kids with refractory epilepsy, the MAD may be a better first-line dietary therapy because it has been linked to improved tolerability and fewer adverse effects [6].

The effectiveness and safety of several dietary interventions, such as the ketogenic diet, modified Atkins diet, and low glycaemic index therapy, were assessed in children with drug-resistant epilepsy by a systematic review and network meta-analysis. According to the study, all dietary interventions reduced the frequency of seizures by 50% or more when compared to usual care. Among these, the MAD was thought to be a good substitute for the traditional KD because it demonstrated improved tolerability [7].

An additional investigation looked at the diversification of dietary therapy choices outside of the traditional ketogenic diet, emphasising less restrictive diets such as the MAD and (LGIT). The research highlighted that these substitutes might increase adherence while preserving seizure control, providing patients and carers with a more tolerable choice [8].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study results strongly suggest that dietary therapy can be an effective and well-tolerated intervention for reducing seizure frequency and improving the quality of life in pediatric patients with epilepsy, particularly in those who have not responded adequately to conventional AEDs. The significant improvements observed in seizure control and quality of life highlight the potential of dietary interventions as a valuable adjunctive treatment for managing epilepsy in children.

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